

-Chemistry Workshop-

Investigation of the Fractional Distillation of an
Acetone-Water Mixture

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1. Introduction:

1.1 Background

Distillation is a purification method for liquids, and can separate components of the mixture if they have significantly different boiling points. In the process of distillation (figure 1), a mixture of liquids is boiled in a distilling flask, in which the liquid vaporizes, travels through a condenser and transforms back into liquid again to drip down to a separate flask for collection (called a distillate). At a given temperature, while one liquid will be able to vaporize as a cause of its low boiling point, the second liquid will remain in the distilling flask, in its original state throughout the distillation process as a result of its significantly higher boiling point.

Fractional Distillation is a type of distillation which separates multiple distillates from a homogeneous liquid mixture, thus involving the collection of multiple samples/distillates. These distillates will have varying amounts of the liquid substances in the initial mixture depending on at what temperature they were collected. The process will continue until pure fractions of both liquids are able to be collected.

Figure 1: Visual Demonstration of Distillation Apparatus and Process

An example of a mixture suitable for purification by the distillation method is an acetone-water solution, which is the focus of this experiment. The abundance of liquid acetone and water can be detected through the use of cobalt (II) chloride. When mixed together with the liquid substance, the cobalt (II) chloride will cause a colour change in the liquid depending on its contents. If the liquid is acetone, it will turn into a blue colour, whereas for water, this colour will be red-ish pink. The mixture of the two liquids will result in a violet/purple colour result. This piece of information will support our experiment and aid us in reaching and evaluating our data.

1.2 Theory

Additional useful values for this experiment include the boiling points of the chosen liquids. The boiling point of acetone is 56°C , whereas the boiling point of water is 100°C . This means that acetone will boil way before the water can, so from this experiment, it can be

expected that we collect the fraction of acetone samples first, as the acetone will be the first to vapourize and ultimately condense into the sample beaker.

In this experiment, we will explore the fractional distillation process of an acetone-water mixture, where we will collect 4 samples of distillate at certain times, and test their contents by reacting them with cobalt (II) chloride. This will help us gain a deeper understanding of the process of fractional distillation, and the purification process of a mixture of two liquids, and their gradual separation.

2. Variables:

- Independent
 - Temperature of mixture
 - Instance of distillate collection
- Dependant variable
 - Composition of distillate samples
 - Temperature of distillation at each fraction collected
- Constant(s)
 - Ratio (and volume) of liquids in the mixture
 - Liquid used in the mixture (acetone and water)
 - Heat supply rate (constant heat supply)
 - Distillation Apparatus
- Control
 - Mixing pure acetone with cobalt(II) chloride → Blue (indicates the presence of mostly acetone)
 - Mixing pure water with cobalt(II) chloride → Pink (indicates the presence of mostly water)

3. Materials & Supplies:

- 1 x 250cm³ Round Bottom Flask
- Boiling Stones
- 2x Measuring cylinder, 50 mL ± 1
- Metal Stand
- Metal Handle/clamp
- Condenser
- Heating Mantle
- 1x 100°C thermometer
- 4 x Beaker
- Test tube stand
- 3 x Test Tubes

- Acetone
- Mineralized Water
- Cobalt (II) Chloride
- 2 x pipette
- Spatula Spoon
- 2x Rubber Tubing
- Notepad

Figure 2: Photo of gathered materials for the experiment

4. Methodology:

4.1 Steps

1. Using 2 different pipettes, measure 2cm^3 of acetone and 2cm^3 of water, and pour each of them into a testing tube. Place the testing tubes in the test tube stand.
2. Measure 1cm^3 of each liquid, and create a mixture of 1:1 ratio and pour it into a 3rd test tube. Place the test tube next to the other 2 test tubes.
3. Take small amounts of cobalt (II) chloride using a spatula spoon, and place one into each test tube. This is in order to establish a control variable and observe color change in different liquids. For water, the cobalt (II) chloride will react to form a red-ish pink color. For acetone, the cobalt (II) chloride will react to form a blue color. For the mixture, the resultant colour will be purple/violet.
4. Prepare a 100cm^3 mixture of water and acetone, each 50cm^3 , using the measuring cylinders.
5. Drop the boiling stones into the round bottom flask, followed by the liquid mixture. The boiling stones will allow for a smooth vaporisation without intense bubbling, and will support a more secure distillation.
6. Secure the round bottom flask using a clamp on the metal stand.
7. Connect the round-bottom flask to the distillation head and secure it properly.

8. Insert a thermometer into the thermometer adapter and attach it to the distillation head, ensuring the thermometer bulb is just below the sidearm to accurately measure the vapor temperature.
9. Attach the condenser to the sidearm of the distillation head.
10. Secure the condenser in place using a clamp on the metal stand.
11. Connect rubber tubing to the condenser, ensuring that the lower end is connected to the cold water inlet and the upper end is connected to the water outlet (placed in the sink).
12. Position the receiving beaker at the condenser's outlet to collect the distilled liquid.
13. Place the heating mantle or Bunsen burner under the round-bottom flask.
14. Gradually increase the heat to bring the liquid mixture to a controlled boil.
15. Observe the process and wait until the first drops appear in the receiving beaker. Wait until the temperature on the thermometer steadies, and collect the first fraction of the distillate. The temperature on the thermometer should read somewhere in between 56°C- 60°C, around 4°C increase from the first boiling point of liquid. Record collection temperatures on notepad.
16. Once collected, quickly replace the beaker with a clean and empty one. Leave the collected distillate sample to the side.
17. Repeat the process for the second portion. This portion should be collected in the temperatures of somewhere in between 64°C-70°C. Record collection temperatures on notepad.
18. Replace the 2nd beaker with the 3rd, and collect the third fraction of the distillate during temperatures in the range of 70°C - 99°C. This is just before reaching water's boiling point. Note down the collection temperatures on the notepad once again.
19. For the last fraction of sample, collect liquid until it has approximately equal volume of substance compared to the previous fractions of distillates. This is expected to be purely water. Do not wait to get all of the liquid condensed, because this will be very uselessly time consuming. Only a certain amount of liquid is needed.
20. Once all 4 fractions are collected in the beakers, take small amounts of cobalt (II) chloride using a spatula spoon once again, and drop one into each of the beakers.
21. Observe and note down the colour change in each fraction of the distillates. This will reveal which fractions contained which liquid. Just water? Just acetone? Some amounts of both liquids? This will vary depending on the number of the fraction which was collected.

4.2: Experiment Photos of Process:

Figure 3: Photo of set up distillation apparatus and its ongoing process

5. Results and Findings:

After conducting the experiment and executing it according to the given methodology, here are the recorded temperatures for our distillate fraction collections in the data table (Figure 4):

Fraction of Distillate	Temperatures of Collection
1st	52°C - 58°C
2nd	59°C - 62°C
3rd	62°C - 100°C
4th	100°C - 110°C

Figure 4: Collection temperatures of each fraction

Following photos are the before and after pictures of the four collected fractions of distillates from the fractional distillation.(Figure 5 & 6)

Figure 5: Labeled Order of Fractions of Distillates Prior to Testing Content with Cobalt (II) Chloride

Figure 6: Resultant colours after the addition of cobalt (II) chloride into the liquid distillates.

6. Data Analysis & Evaluation:

Looking at the data table (figure 4), the temperature intervals seem to align with the requirements of the methodology, however it is noticeable that the liquid collection begins at 52°C, rather than 56°C which is the actual boiling point of acetone. This may have been caused due to false reading of the thermometer by us: the observers, or the slightly false calibration of the thermometer itself. We can calculate the percentage uncertainty for the boiling point of acetone in this experiment:

$$\text{Percentage Uncertainty} = (\text{Absolute Uncertainty} / \text{Expected Value}) \times 100$$
$$4/56 \times 100 = 7.14\%$$

For such an experiment, this can be considered quite a large uncertainty, especially for something that shouldn't be able to change, like the boiling point of a compound. However, fortunately this did not have a significant effect on our data collection nor results/conclusion, since the experiment focused on the approximate contents of each fraction in terms of the types of liquids, not getting too precise.

From the observed colours (figure 6), we see that in the first two fractions of the collection of distillate, the content of the liquid is acetone. This makes sense since these samples were collected in temperatures way below 100°C, meaning the water couldn't have mixed into the product because it wasn't capable of vaporizing at temperatures below 100°C.

However, looking at the 3rd fraction, we see that the blue color is on the verge of turning into a more purple colour. Since this sample was collected in between the temperatures of 62°C - 100°C, water could've mixed into the distillate prior to collecting the sample, especially since we already figured that the reading of the thermometer had complications to it. The mixture of the two substances will make the colour of the mixture violet/purple, so we are able to recognize the abundance of water in the 3rd beaker.

Looking at the 4th and last receiving beaker, we see that the liquid inside has been turned into a red-ish colour after the addition of cobalt (II) chloride. This shows that the 4th fraction is the water itself, and proves that experiment to be quite successful.

Other than more precise temperature control, a possible improvement to the experiment could've been collecting more liquid for the 4th fraction so that the colour would be more clear once mixed with the cobalt (II) chloride, since there would be more liquid to observe, and the colors would be less faded that way, however it did give the overall idea and more that the last fraction of the sample was composed of water itself.

7. Conclusion:

The experiment successfully demonstrated the principles of fractional distillation, showing a gradual separation of acetone and water based on their boiling points. The temperature data and qualitative testing confirmed the effectiveness of the process, though minor discrepancies highlight potential sources of error.

Now, Is distillation the most efficient method for separating acetone and water?

No, while distillation effectively separated the components, it was time-consuming and required constant monitoring. Additionally, some acetone was lost due to early evaporation, and the separation was not 100% pure. However, it did help us gain a better understanding of fractional distillation and enhance our knowledge on many separation and testing methods for substances, and our process was overall successful. With future improvements, it can be taken even further.